

Aminolysis and *Trans*-Esterification Reactions on *Bis*(Ethyl Acetoacetato)Copper(II)*

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Aminolysis of copper(II) chelate of ethyl acetoacetate is found to be a convenient and general method for synthesising copper(II) chelate of acetoacetanilides. The β -ketoester chelate also undergoes facile *trans*-esterification reaction leading to copper(II) chelates of other β -ketoesters, some of which are otherwise difficult to prepare. The complexes have been characterised through their physical constants (when known), analytical data and ir spectra.

THE findings that copper(II) chelates of acetoacetanilides yield on pyrolysis, aryl isocyanates¹ prompted us to search for a convenient method of synthesis of copper(II) chelates of acetoacetanilides bearing different substituents on the phenyl ring. Aminolysis of copper(II) chelate of ethyl acetoacetate was found to yield the desired complexes directly. *Trans*-esterification reactions also occurred. These are substitution reactions of pendant group of metal chelate rings. Substitution of chelate ring hydrogen of β -dicarbonyl complexes has been reported in recent years².

Experimental

A typical procedure for aminolysis reactions is as follows :

To a boiling solution of *bis*(ethyl acetoacetato)-copper(II) (1 g, 0.0033 mole) in xylene (30 ml) was added a solution of aniline (1.8 ml, 0.02 mole) in xylene (25 ml) dropwise. The mixture was refluxed for 3 hr, and then cooled and the crystals formed recrystallised from acetone. Details of complexes so prepared are brought out in Table 1.

The following general method was used for *trans*-esterification reactions. Copper(II) chelate of ethyl acetoacetate was refluxed in excess of the appropriate alcohol for 9 hr. The resulting solution was then concentrated to obtain crystals of the transformed metal chelate, which was then recrystallised from the corresponding alcohol. Table 2 brings out details of the complexes prepared thus, and of the precursor complex.

Infrared spectra of 'Nujol' mulls were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 137 spectrometer. Spectral data in the carbonyl region are included in the tables.

Results and Discussion

The acetoacetanilide complexes prepared were identified through their physical constants^{3,4}, infrared spectra and analytical data. In the presence of mineral acids, the corresponding acetoacetanilide ligands were liberated, which were identified through mixed melting point with authentic samples⁵⁻⁷.

Aniline is reported to react with ethyl acetoacetate yielding also β -anilinoacronate⁸. No such

TABLE 1—COPPER(II) CHELATES OF ACETOACETANILIDES

Copper(II) chelate of	Yield (%)	m.p. (°C)	m.p. of ligand (°C)	Analytical Data*		$\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ (acetyl) (cm^{-1})	$\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ (amide)
				Cu (%)	N (%)		
Acetoacetanilide	76	212	85	14.82 (15.28)	6.54 (6.74)	1577	1608
Acetoacet-2- methylanilide	18	310 d	104	14.08 (14.31)	5.91 (6.32)	1565	1590
Acetoacet-3- methylanilide	49	184 d	57-58	14.23 (14.31)	6.11 (6.32)	1580	1620
Acetoacet-4- methylanilide	74	202 d	95	14.11 (14.31)	6.12 (6.32)	1585	1630
Acetoacet-2- methoxyanilide	28	178-180 d	87	13.19 (13.35)	5.66 (5.89)	1608	1615
Acetoacet-4- methoxyanilide	58	191-192 d	116-117	13.02 (13.35)	5.72 (5.89)	1585	1620

d=Decomposed.

*Calculated percentages in brackets.

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TABLE 2—COPPER(II) CHELATES OF β -KETOESTERS

Compound	Yield (%)	m.p. (°C)	% of copper*	ν C=O (acetyl) (cm ⁻¹)	ν C=O (ester) (cm ⁻¹)
<i>Bis</i> (methyl acetoacetato)copper(II)	54	185	21.28 (21.62)	1540	1605
<i>Bis</i> (<i>iso</i> -propyl acetoacetato)-copper(II)	62	186-188	17.92 (18.17)	1548	1604
<i>Bis</i> (<i>iso</i> -amyl acetoacetato)-copper(II)	48	189-192	14.22 (14.46)	1520	1610
<i>Bis</i> (ethyl acetoacetato)copper(II)	65	198	19.91 (19.79)	1555 ⁺	1600 ⁺

* Calculated percentage in brackets.

+ Infrared band positions identical to those reported¹⁰.

complication was observed in the preparation using the metal chelate. The method is of general applicability with primary aryl amines. *N*-alkyl- and *N*-arylanilines did not react under the above conditions. So also, presence of *ortho* substituent on the aniline resulted in decreased yield, presumably due to steric reasons. Aminolysis of simple esters is in the category of nucleophilic substitution at unsaturated carbon⁹, and steric factors are known to play a decisive role in it. As in the case of aminolysis of free esters, that of coordinated ethyl acetoacetate is found to be catalysed by bases like pyridine and diethanolamine. In view of the various similarities observed, a similar mechanism seems plausible for the aminolysis of coordinated ethyl acetoacetate also.

The complexes obtained by alcoholysis, were characterised through analytical and infrared spectral data. Copper(II) chelate of methyl acetoacetate was prepared also directly following the synthetic method for ethyl acetoacetato complex¹⁰. This enabled characterisation of the complex obtained by *trans*-esterification with methanol, also

through mixed melting point and mixed infrared spectrum.

In view of the difficulty of preparing metal chelates of β -ketoesters directly, this indirect method of synthesis should prove beneficial.

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